

Implementation Of Employee Income Benefits Policy (Tpp) At The Regional Development Planning Agency (Bappeda) North Maluku Province

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 23, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 30, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Implementation, Policy, Additional Employee Income, Communication, Disposition, Resources, Bureaucratic Structure, Performance, and Employee Discipline</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5542515</p>	<p><i>Additional Employee Income (TPP) is one form of indirect compensation given in order to improve employee performance, especially the State Civil Apparatus. For this reason, the North Maluku Provincial Government issued Governor Regulation Number 49 of 2018 concerning Provision of Additional Income for Civil Servants. The Regional Planning and Development Agency of North Maluku Province is a Regional Apparatus Organization which has the task of leading, formulating, fostering, directing, coordinating, and evaluating the implementation of work programs in the field of regional planning and development based on the applicable laws and regulations. The success of achieving organizational goals needs to be supported by a good system. Therefore, measurements of the implementation of the intended policy are carried out to see how effective these rules are in improving employee performance through the dimensions of communication, resources, disposition and bureaucratic structure. The results show: There is consistency and clarity in communication factors carried out from decision makers to implementers, while the dimensions of resources, disposition and bureaucratic structure show weaknesses in the fulfillment of supporting infrastructure which are expected to have a positive effect on employee discipline. For this reason, the following are recommended: (1) Fulfillment of supporting infrastructure in the context of improving employee performance and discipline and (2) increasing human resources through training in regional development planning.</i></p>

Introduction

The salary system for State Civil Apparatus (ASN) applied in Indonesia refers to a system of giving a very low basic salary, and does not directly adjust the dynamics of changes in inflation and the cost of living from year to year. This condition has an impact on the weakening of people's purchasing power, including ASN. With the current payroll system, the majority of ASN in Indonesia will find it difficult to support the fulfillment of their daily primary needs every month, even in the category of simple living. This payroll system is believed to be one of the causes of corruption (corruption by need). The form of corruption is to abuse authority by taking advantage of weak legal rules for the purpose of meeting the necessities of life.

Based on the provisions in the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 13 of 2006 concerning Guidelines for Regional Financial Management as amended by Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 59 of 2007 in Article 39 of the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs, it is stated that the provision of additional income to employees can be given based on workload, performance employment, the scarcity of the profession and other objective considerations. In the 2005 Government Regulation concerning Regional Financial Management in Article 63 Paragraph (2) which states that "Local Governments can provide additional income to Regional Civil Servants based on objective considerations by taking into account regional financial capabilities and obtaining DPRD approval in accordance with the provisions of the legislation invitation".

Performance management is a strategic and integrated approach to generating sustainable success for an organization by improving the performance of people working within the organization and by developing the capabilities of teams and individual contributors (Armstrong, 1997). A new paradigm of public administration emerged by formulating a series of ideals and practices related to the use of certain values and norms in the implementation of public service accountability (Herizal, Mukhrijal, & Wance, 2020).

According to Darwin (2000) policy is an action that leads to goals proposed by a person, group or government in a certain environment in connection with certain obstacles while looking for opportunities to achieve the goals / realize the desired goals. According to Woll, policy is a government activity to solve

problems in society, either directly or through various institutions that affect people's lives. According to Agustino, L (1997) that wisdom requires further consideration (more emphasis on one's wisdom), while policy includes the rules that are in it so that policy is more precisely defined as a policy, while wisdom is an understanding of the word wisdom. According to Tuanaya, et al (2020) planning must be adapted to the basic needs of the community.

Meanwhile, according to Dharma (2005), in general the policies are grouped into three, namely:

1. The process of making a policy which is an activity from the formulation to the making of a policy.
2. The implementation process is the implementation of policies that have been formulated
3. The policy evaluation process is a process of reviewing the implementation that has been carried out or in other words looking for answers to what happened as a result of the implementation of certain policies and discussing the methods used and the results achieved.

Van Mater and Van Horn (2001:2) explain that policy implementation emphasizes actions, whether carried out by the government or private individuals (or groups), which are directed to achieve the goals that have been set in a previous policy decision. Public policy evaluation is an activity to assess or see the success and failure of the implementation of a public policy. Therefore, evaluation is an activity of giving value to something "phenomenon" in which it contains certain value judgments (Mustopadidjaja, 2002). Implementation values become the formal basis for public policy planning (Ibrahim, et al, 2021).

Muhajir Darwin (1992:34) argues that "The implementation process is not a mechanism process where each actor will automatically do whatever should be done according to the scenario of policy makers, but is a process of activities that are often complicated, colored by conflicts of interest between the actors involved both as administrators, field officers or target groups". According to Abdul Wahab (1983), a policy implementation process is the whole of the activities or actions taken by individuals or government and private government officials or groups that are directed at achieving the goals outlined in policy decisions. Organizational policy partnerships are a factor in the successful implementation of government organization programs (Tuanaya, & Wance, 2021).

Method

The type of research used in this research is qualitative research. Moleong (2006) suggests that qualitative research is research that is intended to understand the phenomenon of what is experienced by research subjects, for example behavior, perception, motivation, action and others, holistically and by way of description in the form of words and language, in a special natural context by utilizing various scientific methods (Andi, 2012).

In this study, analyze the policies implemented to determine the formulation of policies in order to gain in-depth knowledge about the object of research through an assessment of what exists and is seen. In connection with this, it can be concluded that the type of research is "descriptive qualitative" which is the type of research that is considered appropriate in this study.

The data were obtained through interviews with the parties involved in the research that the researchers did. The parties who are then used as the source of the data in question are: (1). Head of the Regional Development Planning Agency (BAPPEDA) of North Maluku Province. (2). Secretary of the Regional Development Planning Agency (BAPPEDA) of North Maluku Province. (3). Head of the Planning Sub Division of the Regional Development Planning Agency (BAPPEDA) of North Maluku Province. (4). Head of Sub-Section of General Affairs and Personnel of the Regional Development Planning Agency (BAPPEDA) of North Maluku Province. (5). Head of Sub Division of Finance of the Regional Development Planning Agency (BAPPEDA) of North Maluku Province.

Result and Discussion

Implementation of Additional Employee Income Policy

Additional employee income is an addition given to Civil Servants associated with attendance and performance assessments. Regional performance allowances are improvements to existing allowances and will become a specific allowance to spur performance and at the same time ensure fairness in the provision of benefits. Provision of performance allowances In line with the rapid development of the times and the increasingly complex problems faced by the state, there has also been a development of governance to realize good governance with efforts to increase transparency and accountability of state financial management, because This requires a strong governance framework.

Bureaucratic reform is one of the right ways to build people's trust. Bureaucratic reform is a basic change effort in a system whose purpose is to change the structure, behavior, and existence or old habits. The scope of bureaucratic reform is not only limited to processes and procedures, but also related to changes in the level of structure and attitudes and behavior.

This is related to problems that intersect with the development of politics and democracy, nowadays it has given birth to many greater challenges, especially for government institutions. Every government agency is

required to define its vision, mission, and role as a public institution in order to be able to provide the best service for the community.

In line with that, the vision in the context of the development of the field of employment in the future is to prepare civil servants who are professional, able to compete and able to anticipate rapid world developments in various aspects of life so as to be able to improve the quality of service and awareness of the need for quality human resources. follow up with various strategies that can improve employee performance. One strategy to face challenges that are not easy, every organization must redesign its organizational planning, performance management management and human utilization.

Therefore, the reforms carried out in the context of realizing clean and authoritative governance are unlikely to be implemented properly (effectively) without proper welfare from the employees who carry them out. These changes and reforms were carried out to erase the impression of a government that had been considered bad.

Policy implementation is a very important aspect in the entire policy process because public policies that have been made will be useful if implemented. A policy program must be implemented in order to have the desired impact or goal, implementation is seen as a process of interaction between a set of goals and actions that are able to achieve policy goals. Where in the implementation of organizational policies, procedures and techniques are used together and simultaneously.

Based on the policy issued by the Governor of North Maluku through the Regulation of the Governor of North Maluku Number 49 of 2018 concerning Provision of Additional Income for Civil Servants, which are intended for the following purposes: improving employee performance; improve the quality of service to the community; improve employee welfare and improve employee discipline. Then the researcher will discuss the extent of the implementation of the policy by using the theory proposed by George Edward III, as follows:

Communication

Communication is a very important factor because communication is related to the delivery of information, ideas, skills, regulations and others using certain means to those who receive it (Anwar Arifin, 2000:5). Communication relations must be carried out as a form of non-formal information delivery in government organizations (Ibrahim, et al., 2018).

Policy implementation will run effectively if those who carry out the decisions know what they have to do. Communication must be carried out accurately and must be carefully understood by policy implementers.

Communication is a measure of how far the policy in the form of a regulation has been clearly conveyed with the same interpretation and can be carried out consistently with the implementing apparatus of the regulation. According to Edward III, there are three important things that must be considered in the policy communication process, namely transmission, consistency and clarity.

The ongoing communication aspect is carried out through implementation or technical instructions, direct superior orders and coordination between Regional Apparatus Organizations (OPD). Coordination is very necessary, considering that in implementing the Additional Employee Income (TPP) policy it involves other organizations such as the Regional Financial and Asset Management Agency (BPKAD) and the Regional Personnel Agency (BKD). So that the form of communication that is carried out is communication that is internal and communication that is external.

Internal communication that occurs within the Scope of the Regional Planning and Development Agency (BAPPEDA) of North Maluku Province is carried out through regular staff meetings with the Head of BAPPEDA of North Maluku Province which are delivered both formally and informally. This is as stated by the Head of the Regional Development Planning Agency in an interview with the author:

“I have cultivated regular staff meetings not only in terms of strengthening ties of friendship, but also for monitoring and evaluating staff performance in relation to achieving organizational goals. In relation to the TPP, I am guided by the Duties and Functions, especially in areas that carry out coordination in accordance with their respective affairs as well as the Head of the Division in this case who assesses directly related to the performance of his staff, as well as attendance which is delegated directly to the Head of the General and Civil Service Sub-section. as Manager of Employee Discipline together with the Regional Personnel Board.”(24/02/2020).

In line with the statement from the Head of the Regional Planning and Development Agency (BAPPEDA) of North Maluku Province above, this was confirmed through an interview with one of the Heads of Division, namely the Division of Evaluation and Reporting Control (PERAN) and the Head of the General and Personnel Sub-section. The results of the interview with the Head of Evaluation and Reporting Control (Zumarlan Rais Keliobas, S.STP., M.Si) are as follows:

"Regarding the performance in the Control, Evaluation and Reporting Sector, that every task and function that is the responsibility of the field is entirely the responsibility of the field, so that the distribution of work is evenly distributed with the number of staff. Apart from that, the target from the Role Sector towards existing Programs and Activities is running as planned, this is because the division of responsibilities is in accordance with the description of the echelon IV position in charge of per affairs of the existing activities with coordination between the Head of the Field and the Technical Implementation Officer (PPTK) of course."(25/02/2020).

Meanwhile, regarding the discipline of BAPPEDA employees of North Maluku Province, the following is an explanation from the Head of the General and Civil Service Subdivision (Mahmud Ahmad, S.Sos):

"With this Employee Income Allowance (TPP), measuring employee discipline becomes a determining factor after the performance of the amount of TPP received by each Civil Servant in the Scope of the Regional Government of North Maluku Province, especially in the BAPPEDA of North Maluku Province itself. With the implementation of the finger system implemented by the Regional Personnel Agency and in coordination with all Heads of General Affairs and Regional Apparatus Organizations, civil servants began to be orderly in carrying out their obligations, but there were still civil servants who were still lazy in carrying out their obligations to enter the office, thus affecting the achievement of the performance scores obtained. " (24/02/2020).

Based on an explanation from the Head of the General and Civil Service Sub-section, the following is the disciplinary data (Attendance/Attendance) of employees within the Regional Planning and Development Agency (BAPPEDA) of North Maluku Province:

The graph above shows an increase in employee attendance discipline. Although the average value shown during 2019 is in the range of 55.7%.

The data and interview results above illustrate that the communication process carried out in the context of implementing the Additional Employee Income (TPP) policy is running as it should. Obstacles in the communication process such as disagreements between implementers and policy makers, bureaucratic hierarchies, and the transmission process in the communication process did not appear to have occurred. This is due to the consistency and clarity of the communication carried out from the top level to the implementer.

Resource

Implementation instructions may be passed carefully, clearly and consistently. However, if implementers lack the necessary resources to implement policies, then implementation will tend to fail.

Currently, the Regional Planning and Development Agency (BAPPEDA) of North Maluku Province has a total number of 76 employees. The total, then broken down into the number of employees based on education level is as follows:

Table 1. Number of Employees of BAPPEDA of North Maluku Province by Education Level in 2019

No	Employment Status/Education Level	Unit	Total
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		Kaban	Sekretariat	Bidsosbud	BIDEK	BIDIPW	BidPeran	Fungsional	
1	PNS								
	Strata 3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Strata 2	1	4	6	5	2	5		23
	Strata 1		10	3	10	9	6		38
	Diploma						1		1
	SMA/Sederajat		5	2	2		3		11
	SMP								
	SD								
2	PTT								
	Strata 1			1			1		2
Total		1	19	12	18	11	16		76

Source: BAPPEDA of North Maluku Province, 2019.

The following are the results of the researcher's interview with the Head of the Regional Planning and Development Agency (BAPPEDA) of North Maluku Province:

"According to the coordination between the Head of Bappeda and the Regional Personnel Agency and based on the analysis of the existing positions, Bappeda itself is still considered to be short of personnel. From the existing number, 39 people must be added to fill staff vacancies, especially in the sub-sectors in Bappeda. However, until now, it is hoped that the obstacle regarding the shortage of employees will not become a significant obstacle. I think so far the performance of BAPPEDA of North Maluku Province is running optimally." (24/02/2020).

Even though based on the Job Analysis, the number of personnel within BAPPEDA of North Maluku Province is insufficient, this does not become an obstacle in implementing existing programs or activities. that must be carried out by policy implementers in the Scope of BAPPEDA of North Maluku Province. This is because not all Commitment Making Officers (PPK) involve all staff as a whole but only staff who have more technical capabilities for the achievement of organizational performance targets.

Facilities and infrastructure are supporting factors in the implementation of the implementation of a policy and can be used directly to support the assigned tasks. In this case, the budget becomes the determinant in the implementation of the program and or activity in question.

The Regional Planning and Development Agency (BAPPEDA) of North Maluku Province in 2019 managed a budget for approximately 10 programs and or activities of Rp. 10.284.753.900,-. And based on the measurement of performance targets, the performance indicators used as a measure of the success of strategic goals and objectives for the scope of BAPPEDA of North Maluku Province can be seen in the table below:

Table 2. Performance Achievements of BAPPEDA North Maluku Province in 2019

No	Strategy Goal	Performance Indicator	Target	Realization	Achievements (%)
1	The implementation of the regional development planning process according to the correct stages	Percentage of PWD who already have good, consistent and aligned planning documents	90 %	90%	100
2	Improving the quality of implementation of control, evaluation and reporting	Percentage of PDs who have carried out M&E and reporting well	85 %	85%	100
3	Improve the quality of planning data	Percentage of data that can be prepared completely	60 %	60%	100

Source: BAPPEDA of North Maluku Province, 2019.

Regarding the absorption of the budget, based on the data above, it can be seen that even with a limited number of employees, performance achievements within the scope of BAPPEDA of North Maluku Province can be achieved according to the target.

The following are the results of an interview with the Head of the Finance Sub-Section at BAPPEDA of North Maluku Province (Ikram A. Idrus, S.IP) regarding the budget absorption process:

“So far, the absorption of the budget at BAPPEDA is in the good category and can be seen based on the achievement of performance each year, which is in accordance with the target. The obstacles experienced are more to the administrative process and also the rules that the reference budget disbursement process is in accordance with the Accountability Report which must be entered according to the agreed tempo so that it has an impact on the budget process for other activities.” (27/02/2020).

The obstacles faced then became a pile of work for all staff because not only were the numbers small but also the entire staff was not involved in each activity program, as explained by the researcher in the previous paragraph.

Performance is an important thing in an organization's efforts to achieve its goals. Employee performance is measured by quality, quantity and timeliness. If this is managed properly, it will help an organization not only achieve its goals but also be able to maintain and maintain employees properly. Thus, employees will feel more valued so that they are more enthusiastic in improving their performance.

In order to support employee performance, the North Maluku Provincial Government is committed to providing Additional Employee Income (TPP) as regulated in Governor Regulation No. 49 of 2018. The following is the amount of additional employee income based on position level and data on the realization of employee budget absorption, especially in the Scope of Provincial BAPPEDA North Maluku in 2019:

Table 3. Report on the Realization of Employee Budget Expenditures on Additional Income for Civil Servants Based on Classification of Fund Sources for the Period 1 January to 31 December 2019

Description	Budget	Realization	Percentage
Direct Shopping			
Employee Shopping			
Spending Additional Income for Civil Servants	2.052.458.000,-	1.985.921.941,-	96%
- Additional Income Based on Workload	899.918.000,-	833.381.941,-	92%
- Additional Income Based on Objective Considerations	1.152.540.000,-	1.152.540.000,-	100%

Source: North Maluku Province BPKAD, 2019.

The data above, then the researcher confirmed with the Head of the Finance Sub Division at BAPPEDA North Maluku Province (Ikram A. Idrus, S.IP) through interviews as follows:

"Regarding the budgeting for the payment of Additional Employee Income (TPP) it is included in the Indirect Expenditure (BTL) category including salaries and allowances which are managed directly by the Financial Management and Regional Assets Revenue Agency (BPKPAD) of North Maluku Province, so the Regional Apparatus Organization proposes an amount that must be paid according to the procedures that have been regulated, one of which is through the calculation of the Employee Performance Unit (SKP)". (04/03/2020).

Employee Income Supplemental Revenue (TPP), which is the result of performance appraisal and employee attendance, is still not effective and efficient. Through an interview with one of the staff of BAPPEDA of North Maluku Province (Kurniati Sillia, SH, MURP) regarding the workload with additional employee income he received, the following responses were given:

"The attitude of the ASN in North Maluku Province to the Regulation of the Governor of North Maluku No. 49 of 2018 concerning Additional Income Allowances is considered inadequate due to the high transportation costs for ASN who live outside Sofifi due to the lack of accommodation provided for ASN in the North Maluku Province. However, with the Governor's Regulation no. 7 of 2019 is considered to be more adequate and sufficient to accommodate transportation costs that must be incurred by ASN in the Prov. North Maluku, especially those who live in Ternate on average". (27/02/2020).

The analysis above illustrates that the implementation of additional employee income policies has not been supported by effective and efficient resources. Although the resulting performance is optimum, this cannot be categorized as good. Changes to the rules or policies for Additional Employee Income (TPP) are expected to increase enthusiasm for the resulting performance. However, another solution that must be considered is the equitable distribution of tasks through empowerment in terms of quality and increasing the number of staff in the BAPPEDA Scope of North Maluku Province.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and analysis that has been carried out and the discussion described in the previous chapter, it can be concluded that the Additional Employee Income (TPP) has an effect on the performance of Civil Servants, Regional Apparatus Organizations, Regional Development Planning Board of North Maluku Province, will increase if employee discipline runs well. good, but if employee discipline is low it will have the opposite impact, so it can be concluded several important points as follows:

1. The communication factor through Governor Regulation Number 49 of 2019, is fully understood, especially by Civil Servants within the scope of BAPPEDA of North Maluku Province. Communication is a measure of how far the policy in the form of a regulation has been clearly conveyed with the same interpretation and can be carried out consistently with the implementing apparatus of the regulation.
2. Resource factors include Implementation orders may be passed carefully, clearly and consistently. However, if implementers lack the necessary resources to implement policies, then implementation will tend to fail. The following are some benchmarks to see how far the implementation of this policy has gone:
 - a. Sufficiency and Qualifications
 - b. Authority
 - c. Information
 - d. Facilities and infrastructure
3. Disposition factors include A policy will be successfully implemented if policy implementers not only know the existing regulations, but understand what they must do and also have the ability and willingness and good attitude to implement existing policies.
4. There are still Civil Servants who do not carry out their obligations to enter the office, so it seems that the application of existing employee discipline is weak even though verbal and written warning actions have been taken and cannot be proposed in receiving the Employee Income Supplemental Reward (TPP).

Acknowledgment

Our gratitude goes to the Director of Postgraduate Masters in Administrative Sciences, University of Muhammadiyah North Maluku who has provided input and support so that this research can be carried out to completion.

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